

Seventy years after humans invented software, humanity realizes that it is no longer under its control but has entered a symbiotic co-evolution.

Extreme reuse: the only future any code can afford

BY THOMAS HOBERG

Software engineers tend to see themselves as designers or architects, true creators of things new, perhaps even optimal. That may have been true for the early pioneers, who created algorithms that many considered “art”. But to understand what is happening in the IT industry, we should perhaps regard ourselves as mutating the code base of that species of software, with which we have entered into symbiosis. We are a bit like a virus, an agent of evolution, which has software adapt to a changing world.

Key insights

- While the cost of storing code has fallen exponentially for decades, the cost of creating good new code remains dramatically high: because nobody can afford clean design, code only evolves and includes potentially dangerous atavisms or leftovers.
- The energy investment vs. the value of computation becomes so dominant, that both start controlling the execution and the quality of the results opportunistically.
- The complexity of systems follows the complexity of society and its digitalization: specialization and differentiation deepen, aggregates evolve, interdependence and fragility increase as a consequence of economic optimization.
- The evolution, success, sustainability and life span of large bodies of software and programming languages critically depend on the quality and the investment of the communities around it. Those communities may require significant initial and long-term support to achieve and sustain critical size.
- Revolutionary from scratch designs only tend to work in isolation or on a green field. Where there is an existing competitor, they tend to fail even if that has significant defects. But when the pressure is high enough, that may evolve so rapidly, it looks completely new.
- There is no natural process to clean up code no longer used, not in genetics, not in software, not in social code. That creates significant vulnerabilities.
- Cost reduction pushes legacy code into IoT devices creating critical risks that we need novel ways to manage.

Key recommendations

- Accept that some legacy code will live in niches much longer than anyone planned for. It requires dedicated support in education, but may return value in excess of that cost.
- Only failure, potentially catastrophic, will clean up unmaintained legacy code: regulate and support the creation of evolutionary pressure beforehand to reduce the risk.
- Ensure regulation to assure a minimum of quality where safety and resilience are needed to counteract the overwhelming temptation of cutting & pasting legacy code into use cases and domains it was never designed for.
- Invest into defensive technology for the trusted base like control flow hardening, randomization, SoC IP blocks for application level firewalls.
- Where bad legacy code keeps getting recycled, support process and assets so that manufacturers of even the cheapest IoT devices can be convinced to switch to an EU-maintained high quality base.
- Support research in tools that help with refactoring and black-boxing legacy code, translating it into safer languages, or help with annotation for automated testing and entry-exit checks at black-box borders.
- Support a world-leading community of compiler maintainers capable of extending mainline compilers like LLVM or specialty compilers like SPARK with resilience features e.g. for control-flow integrity, memory capabilities or tagging support.
- Support legacy code and documentation data bases with smarter tooling to find code similarities and discover build tool dependencies.
- Support research into value-driven computing, which adapts its processing dynamically to the value of input data, as a key paradigm extension for sustainability.

Some history

During World War II critical mass was reached for the atom bomb and the computer era:

- Alan Turing proved that even the most complex mathematical problem could be divided into a series of rather primitive; logic operations given sufficient memory
- Electronic implementations of that logic blasted the speed barriers of mechanics away;
- John von Neuman proposed encoding the sequence of operations in the same memory as data to create software.

Earlier computers had to be physically rebuilt for each new task, now software enabled evolution with code: existing solutions could be cut & pasted whenever and wherever a similar problem needed solving and re-used with a minimum of incremental adaptation.

It enabled Grace Hopper to design high-level languages which allowed an algorithm to be expressed at a human level of abstraction while the computer itself would then translate it into the primitive machine instructions for execution. High-level language code is easier to write, read, understand and re-use by people and allows users to build the most complex applications from small well-designed and tested building blocks. The same principle applies to hardware, which combines libraries of primitive logic functions into layers and stacks of higher-level aggregates to implement the most complex chips, while it is implemented in a hardware description language first and “compiled” into silicon after.

The invention of integrated circuits created aggregates of transistor logic on silicon using photo-lithography reaching several billion gates over four decades on a single chip today, shrinking the etched structures from 10µm in 1971 to 10nm in 2016 or by a factor of 1000:1 along both sides, while the yield in transistors exploded in squares.

The incredibly rich functionality of current hardware and software is enabled by mind-boggling complexity and only possible because each design iteration was

evolutionary, re-using and incrementally expanding the functional base for the last seven decades. The functional expansion of code, its ability to do things quicker than mechanics and much more complex than discrete electronics had it replace both, because process shrinks eliminated the markup of physical complexity while software enabled economy of scale for hardware more generic than discrete solutions.

But it is also based on an architecture which solves even the largest problem by breaking it down into a sequence of very small steps, executed by a general-purpose CPU on a memory space that is shared between code and data.

Initially operations on larger numbers had to be broken down into a sequence of operations on individual digits, just like we learned to do sums in elementary school. Likewise, a single high-level language operation, such as a multiplication, would be broken down into a sequence of machine level operations by a compiler or internally by the CPU itself. That didn't matter, because the competition was manual or mechanical and electronical computers were getting faster very quickly. Cycle times shrunk x4000 in the three formative decades of personal computers ((1972-2002 740KHz (8008) to 3GHz (Pentium IV)), while the work completed per cycle also increased via the widening of the architec-

ture from 4/8-bit to 64-bit and by pipelining complex instructions to the point where all operations on scalar data types finish, on average, within a single cycle. The combined effect was a scalar speed boost of x500000 for a line of Cobol code written in 1972 and running in 2002.

Computers became so fast so quickly, that their human operators could not keep up and had to be replaced by a piece of software called the operating system to organize batches of jobs. They were so fast, that they could be multiplexed among several, even hundreds of users, each of whom would seem to have the computer to themselves. In the art and science of software engineering generations of students were trained to break every problem into small reusable sequences of easy-to-understand code. Practically all current operating systems, programming languages and the vast majority of existing code assets were created on this architecture where the central processing unit was so fast, it was cut into tiny time slices to share among many workloads.

But at the dawn of the new millennium that changed fundamentally when silicon physics hit the “Gigahertz Wall (or alternatively as the breakdown of the Dennard scaling)” [1] and a sharp uptake in energy consumption and heat erected vertical barriers to economical operation beyond

Source: <https://www.karlsruhp.net/2018/02/42-years-of-microprocessor-trend-data/>

that point. The physical and economical barriers of process shrinks rise somewhat slower, but the effect of both on the economy of software is much bigger.

For a brief moment two decades ago, high-level languages and CPUs met on equal footing, as every statement expressed in a high-level language could be translated into a machine level equivalent delivering a result every cycle at the maximum speed of silicon physics. At that point, the architecture of CPUs could no longer be improved without sacrificing general purpose and high-level languages. As sequential operations on scalar data types could no longer be sped up, going parallel was the only way forward.

Special purpose vector extensions were developed for scientific computing as early as 1960 [2] and have since even trickled down into smartphones. A single such instruction can easily require several pages of high-level code to replicate functionally for a scalar CPU. In fact, programmers would have little choice but to write such code, both for portability and because “high-level” languages offer no vector intrinsics: while the programmer may be well aware of a hardware’s vector facilities and tries to organize his scalar

loops for easy unrolling, he relies on the compiler and sometimes on annotations (much a secondary programming language hidden in comments, that a normal or non-vectorizing compiler would ignore) to turn his loops into vector operations for the expected speedup. Where the nature of the problem permits and the pressure on speed outweighs the pain of writing and testing such code, it is used as long as it delivers advantages.

With scalar CPU power exhausted, the transistor windfall from process shrinks led into a veritable ‘core explosion’, 4 to 64 cores between 2006 and 2019 on a desktop budget, even smartphones regularly have 8 or more CPU cores today, while the cores in the graphics processing part of their system on chip (SoC) count in thousands. The processing units of these GPUs trade a much simpler per-core design for vastly greater numbers on the same silicon die area. As a consequence, they operate at perhaps 1/10 comparable CPU speed per core with traditional sequential code, but when you’re able to put a 1000 of them, each with 8-64x (Depending on precision: 8x for FP64, 64x for INT8 are typical) vector extensions, to operate on a problem in closely synchronized lock-step, they deliver 100x CPU (or 800-6400x scalar

speed) performance at similar transistor and electricity budgets, but not with Cobol source code.

The last two decades have seen an almost complete inversion of how we need to operate and program computers. For half a century processor speeds increased at a pace, where iteration was discarded as a limitation. Instead operating systems focused on loading as many parallel tasks as possible on systems to avoid idle time, while programmers made iteration and induction the most important ingredients of programming languages and algorithms to create the highest quality and reusable code.

Today any single social media application, HPC workload, ERP system, even a leading smartphone app need to marshal thousands if not billions of heterogeneous computing cores to satisfy or convince their user base within the tiny time and energy budget these applications can afford without losing user attention or to a competing service.

Imagine cooking for Christmas or building a brick and mortar house: the first few helpers offer quick gains but a hundred or a thousand extra hands require re-inventing

the process or rewriting the software from scratch, to avoid logjam. As a result, the expressive power of high-level languages today sits far below hardware level instructions, and their essential contribution to the economy of software, portability and reusability, is lost.

This affects seven decades of software heritage, almost every line of code ever written in a high-level language. Loops, once a clear indication a programmer had been able to abstract and generalize a problem, now just prove a workload was neglected to be parallelized. Code is no longer both, the universal inductive proof of mathematical correctness as well as the solution to the problem. Instead it has become a bundle of marching orders organizing wave-fronts of handlers on a specific machine with custom instructions, where neither the approach nor the purpose can even be guessed back from reading the source.

Code gets ever more expensive to create and cheaper to copy

The first computers had so precious little memory, even code was external, requiring physical re-assembly to change the computational sequence. Only critical reference data was kept in RAM and all other inputs were fed from punch cards or ticker tapes, while output went straight to paper output or again punch cards/ticker tapes for reuse. It was cheaper and larger memory that enabled the sequencing logic to be represented as code in the same memory and thus enabled the software revolution. Even so, only the most abstracted data – typically numbers – were processed in the old days. But with the cost of memory falling exponentially, data grew similarly, while code growth was much more linear, if that.

Creating code to perform a task remains expensive; correct, efficient, resilient, secure and trustable code much more so. But the encoding requires miniscule amounts of memory, especially if you compare it to data like video. Programmers may write a hundred lines of code per day, much smaller than a single video frame, millions of which anyone with a smartphone can produce with little more effort than a stiff arm.

What makes coding affordable is reuse: programmers no longer start on a green field but can copy seven decades of problem-solving know-how with a keystroke or mouse click, before they write the first new line of code. With that they resemble life on Earth, where everything that lives does that very same thing: first the full genetic repository gets copied and then is used to run life of the organism. A few mutations will get transcribed into the genome of future generations and selection then picks a winner on each cycle; code grows and differentiates depending on the habitat and the speed varies with selection pressure. That genetic repository is full of solutions that worked at least at one point in time of that species' evolution, but in the case of the human genome, perhaps as little as 10% is still in active use today.

The code base rarely shrinks, neither in IT nor in nature, because the slight increase in memory space is cheaper than cleaning up code. It's only when disused code contains vulnerabilities to foreign virus code attacks that it becomes a liability and ceases to be passed on to a next generation.

The extremely high cost of producing new code is typically offset by its very wide, if not global, distribution. But that usually just works out, when you reach that scale. Shrink-wrapped commercial software rode on the wave of personal computers selling millions of copies, at a time when code size still mattered and distribution could be controlled. The internet and compute density improvements make it possible to pretty much store all applications ever produced for a field of interest on a normal PC resulting in tumbling revenues from commercial software. The vendors who survived have learned to create lock-in and addiction, subsidizing convenience and a low initial effort or price and charging when the effort of changing habits seems more costly than paying up to the vendor.

From fixed function or purpose to meta programming

Originally every program was written for a single purpose, even if iterating over many different input data sets. As systems became bigger and more complex, they were soon split into specialized reusable

pieces, copied and re-assembled for similar and other tasks with minimal extensions. Today we have ERP systems, constructed much like the factory floors and supply chains they operate, or interactive software instruments that allows us to create or assemble at a higher level with them, meta design or programming tools. They could just be rich documents and spreadsheets with formulas or macros, databases with queries and triggers, CAD software with parametric design or physics simulation plug-ins far more costly than the base application, websites with much more code than content, or it could be complex animations, simulations or game worlds of galactic proportions using several layers of automation and different ones for outside appearance, content behaviour and the interactions with hundreds of thousands of participants in a single game world.

Because “interactive” means human and manual, wherever a critical mass accumulates, APIs handle-bars are added to enable further automation, perhaps even with AI and we see a trend for orchestration languages, some very domain-specific, to code and operate at this meta-level... which may then go through a similar process on the next layer.

The affordability of clouds comes from the degree of automation they achieve with their many-layered global operating system. Facebook is extreme, a single application controlling millions of servers and capturing billions of users and their devices, using perhaps dozens of meta programming levels. It is interactive the other way around, with consumers reacting to machine inputs generated from code and AI bots.

Evolution at very different paces

But while new types of code and systems are developed, they don't universally replace all of the old ones. They solve arising challenges and may use new approaches to do so. They cause a Cambrian explosion of software and hardware species where the evolutionary pressure is fiercest, but other areas, even important ones, see hardly any change. It follows the same patterns as nature, where we still see the most primitive single cell life forms dating back to

the origins of life, past coelacanths little changed over the last 100 million years to the wide variety of Darwin finches [3], who had to exploit every Galapagos island niche, but whose homeland only emerged from the sea as recently as 3 million years ago.

Software follows the rewards

The mobile phone apps market resembles Galapagos in the sense that both Android and iOS rose from the sea with only the bare minimum of programming tools necessary to launch life, but a huge potential market. To tap into it, programmers had little choice but to learn the language chosen by the eco system creator, Objective-C for iOS, a variant of Java for Android, and dive deeply into the respective APIs, libraries and toolchains. Cobol and Fortran never made it across the internet ocean from server continents to the mobile island even if their operating systems build on Unix roots.

The frantic pace of mobile app development created such high stress on both Java and Objective-C, that new programming languages sprung from the need to code more efficiently, but still perfectly molded into the dominating paradigm: Kotlin [4] is undistinguishable from Java to Android, once the compiled code arrives as an app. Swift [5] likewise makes a huge productivity difference for the application developer, but none whatsoever for the iOS platform once compiled.

Programmers flock to these languages because in the mobile apps space, few things are as crucial as being the first to offer a new service and the most aggressive to add new variants and features, outpacing any competitor who ends up asphyxiated from lack of download revenues on pages 2 to 400 of the app store, where few potential clients ever wander.

The Go [6] language was created at Google as an alternative to C and to avoid C++ mainly because with those the repetitive parsing of include files slowed the recompilation of Google's giant and constantly changing code base adding multi-processing and networking support within the language. Principle use cases are

scale-out orchestration code like Docker and Kubernetes, or most of what runs the server side of the Internet.

The Rust [7] language was created by Mozilla for the opposite end, with the principal focus on safe multi-core programming within a single application, the browser in this case. The browser has become the single most important application on all client platforms and a hotly contended battleground for software supremacy. In both cases the single original use case was under such intense evolutionary pressure for safe efficiency because of the giant scale of its application (millions of servers, billions of users), that it seemed to justify a new language to ease the pain of constant refactoring of the most critical parts alone. Both languages are also seeing adoption outside those initial use cases, but without that pressure and importance, sticking with C or its derivatives would have been the lesser effort and path most likely taken.

SPARK [8] was defined as a formally verified subset of ADA for use in flight or train control systems, where formal proof methods were required for verifiably safe operation, much smaller bodies of code than a browser or cloud orchestration system. But where Rust aims at avoiding crashing thousands of browsers every second with monthly releases, SPARK's aim is to avoid thousands of planes carrying hundreds of passengers at every moment ever crashing over two or three decades of operation and software release cycles somewhat less agile.

At the same time, we see extremely specialized software packages for oil field extraction or car crash simulation that carries a price tag of millions for a single installation, so nobody bothers adapting it to run more efficiently using the lower-cost accelerator capabilities of modern hardware: with only dozens or thousands of installations on the planet, the cost of refactoring the code easily exceeds the price tags of the biggest traditional scale-up hardware.

Value-driven computation

IT has always been cost-conscious if only because early computers were as expensive as spaceships. Yet where until recently IT calculated its business case within a relatively static Total Cost of Ownership (TCO) model outside an applications view, the huge scale-out applications Facebook, Google, Amazon and their Chinese counterparts are running need to calculate their profit and loss balance continually themselves. They sell or use the power to change consumers' minds: their business model could be described as venture analytics or electron capitalism in the sense that they constantly need to weigh the energy-dominated cost of their computations against the value they generate. And that value is much more limited than the computing capacity available. They are paid by producers of goods and services either to influence consumer purchasing decisions directly via advertisement or indirectly via analytics and recommendations, but marketing and sales cost can only be a part of the final purchase price, typically small.

Perhaps the amount of data will continue to explode, but there is no reason why consumer purchasing power would follow that trend. It may actually suffer from human workforces competing ever more globally and with robots and AIs, neither of which earn salaries to feed back into economy. Consumers need to pay for necessities first and can be influenced mostly on how they spend what remains. The internet giants hold the steering wheel for content, they can also step on the accelerator, analyze deeper or increase the advertisement ratio, but human consumers are a very slippery road and the giants' business model can lose traction earlier than they expect.

As Google, Amazon and Facebook start stepping on each other's toes in search for growth, they need to become smarter in where they spend energy on analyzing ever bigger amounts of data. Whenever they receive a bit of data, they spend electrons and decide to discard, harvest, forward, correlate, analyze, store, trust, augment, predict, multicast the input in order to generate more value than they invest, while of course the value and the effort are very

dynamic and the consumer still can resist even an optimal recommendation.

Classic computing is built on binary, true or false, correct or invalid. Non-repeatability, or that a piece of code might return distinct results for the same inputs is considered a failure: few of us would accept a bank statement balance preceded by “roughly estimated at...”. Yet with Google searches or Facebook recommendations, not many will complain about missing a match or two while sifting through the millions of responses returned within the blink of an eye (while the fact that certain matches keep getting listed even after data owners had filed for delisting is becoming a growing legal issue). The paradigm that the quality of the result very much depends on the effort invested, and that the effort depends on the potential value, was crucial for evolution of the web giants under economic pressure and is sure to find willing adopters elsewhere.

Value-driven architectures come from the need to no longer just compute or analyze every bit of input given, but to continuously decide on if and how to proceed on data, based on a hunch of its value, tuned in carefully designed feedback loops. From *computing on-demand* it turns into *computing on value opportunity* and the competitive pressure is on extending the depth and the quality of the analysis without raising the cost, much—if not most—of which is energy. And because faster clocks or more instructions per cycle of general-purpose compute has become impossible to obtain economically, it means new hardware and software approaches are required and invented, but always at low budgets and just enough quality.

IoT is similar to the GAFAM business model in that the main enabler and driver is generating more value from data than expended via energy and all other cost and risks. And while most IoT-related services will have their counterparts in the cloud and in perhaps various stations along the path from the edge to the centre, the cost distribution, life cycle requirements may be as different as the things turned smart: some will enjoy a surplus of harvestable energy or sit right on the powerlines as

smart meters, others may need to operate on a single charge for life. And since value and opportunity can be highly dynamic, a device needs to be aware of them. A smart fire alarm will try to conserve energy most of the time, but choose to expend a life’s worth in high-frequency reports when it’s burning, while activity in hybrid solar and battery powered edge devices follows the sun.

The only constants are likely to be severe price pressure and that they’ll rapidly evolve with all essential fidelity wherever competition is most ferocious; they’ll need to take baby steps, as internet giants and IoT can ill afford to stumble in the presence of alternatives, but at extreme speeds to stay ahead.

Value-driven architectures for the Internet of Things must satisfy essential rules and this is the most important one: *while digitalization may expand in number of nodes involved or in the depth of their processing, newer generations of technology cannot cost more than what they replace.*

IoT is also quickly becoming an intrinsic part of the GAFAM business model, and they are the first to try bend that rule: Android devices, smart speakers and household appliances as well as browsers are turned into both sensor data gatherers and the first levels of compute and analytics platforms. Instead of just pushing raw data into their data centres, where they need to pay for energy, web giants try to push as much of the computing workload back towards the edge or client devices. From their standpoint that maintains the primary rule of IoT, because they can go wider and deeper without paying extra: not only are consumers becoming the product [9], now they even pay for being sold.

Designing software is social and human

Programming is a very social activity, even if the actual coding typically requires a high degree of concentration somewhat incompatible with chatter. It starts with the fact that we learn first and best through imitation, just as we learned to speak by listening to our mothers. Reading code that is both well-made and easy to read helps

develop the skill, and it also helps reuse the code.

What you consider easy to read, depends very much on what you have read before and how much time you spend both reading and coding. Cobol [10] reads almost like plain English and was designed so even a non-programmer would be able to make out what it is doing. But it can be as exhausting as some of the old mathematical proofs in the original Greek; the language may be an obstacle, sure, but it’s the lack of a concise mathematical notation (and perhaps a picture), the sheer verbosity required to describe the very abstract, which makes them extra difficult to understand.

APL (A Programming Language) [11] has always represented the opposite corner, offering an extremely concise way of encoding program logic using mathematical symbols instead of English, but to the uninitiated it looks like Klingon. Both languages have enjoyed huge success and for a long time, but never with the same crowds.

But just as surely, even large communities will eventually die, after plenty of small ones have long gone. Sumerian [12], ancient Greek and Latin were commonly spoken only for centuries, but they survived millennia as classic languages for literature, religion and business as long as the content encoded with them remained relevant enough to motivate new disciples to learn and exchange. Cobol, Fortran [13], C [14] and vast bodies of commercial and scientific code written in them may survive in niche communities much longer than expected, but just as with publications in Sumerian, Attic Greek and Latin, the rate of content creation is slowing down significantly, while new dialects and variants continue to flourish best where crowds of enthusiastic users make for fertile ground. RatFor, B, D, Algol [15] and various 4GLs share their fate with Etruscan, Hittite, or Aztec, who despite historical importance and fame, failed to achieve long-term success. When the code or the knowledge encoded with them can’t be black-boxed as a service like sages in a temple, it would need to be re-invented.

Some software dinosaurs will stay with us, many died unnoticed

Life on Earth wasn't designed, which shows in skeletons. The first type, 'exo' or outer skeleton got species moving much faster than mere skin, both to eat and to avoid being eaten, creating huge success and many variants, but also a serious size limitation, especially on land. The size of a specimen is determined as it transitions from the pupa or nymph form into an adult and that's why even the biggest locust won't ever reach the size of a dinosaur, even if size, as dinosaurs proved, can be a giant advantage. But since nobody could afford to throw all that genetic code away and start fresh from a single cell design, some individual popped an organ or a limb outside the shell and made that stick. It even turned it into a full new growth path, where all of the mobility parts had much more room to expand, even to the size of a brontosaurus, which still started with a single cell for every individual, but included genetic code that had long outgrown the limits of an exoskeleton. The 'endo' or inner skeleton was an evolutionary approach, that preserved working code and concentrated change on where it delivered the biggest competitive benefits. We still use exoskeletal code for our head and around our heart, because it doesn't obstruct critical growth there: brains are big enough at birth and ribs are the genius compromise somewhere between exo and endo.

The code that implements the TCP/IP [16] protocol inside an operating system was written to handle the thousands of things that could go wrong, when a data packet was sent from the University of Hawaii to Stanford via dozens of relays over radio in a storm. All of these potential pitfalls are still checked, even when the simulated network between two virtual machines is in fact the single physical memory bus they share for code and data on the host they run on, ... or when that tempestuous radio network is in fact a fabric [17] Google purpose built for their data centres with extreme reliability and transparent fault tolerance. At

the size of Google with millions of physical machines, this needless overhead became so painful that its engineers decided to cut from the code all errors that cannot occur in its fabrics or use cases. Google is now reported to have 100 different implementations matched and directly linked to each application [18], completely circumventing the Linux TCP/IP kernel code, which is still there and even used for booting the machines.

Maintaining such a great number of implementation variants can become quite an effort in itself. But a clean rearchitecting or modularization that is generic enough to pass back to the Linux community for maintenance is also a significant task and a process far too lengthy to perform at the speed Google requires. Generally, code evolution is fastest with the cloud giants, but will still just favour the least effort required to obtain the critical competitive advantage.

In some cases, projects to completely refactor a software stack still occur and succeed, most visibly with browsers, which are among the most important pieces of code in existence, by their concurrent rate of execution with billions of users.

In other cases, their success is rather more limited as with OpenSSL/LibreSSL/BoringSSL [19]. OpenSSL was discovered to have significant cryptographic weaknesses, but the code base was such a huge pile of code from so many sources with questionable quality, that two groups felt it was necessary to restart from scratch. Neither have succeeded to deliver a fully functional replacement so the race is still open, as it will remain in many similar scenarios.

Dinosaurs are still with us: we call them birds. Like browsers they have changed their feathers to the point we don't even realize their legacy roots. Yet while browsers only came to be three decades ago, some Cobol applications continue to run as-a-service in black boxes after decades, simply because there was too little benefit for the cost of a new implementation. Every major ecosystem change will kill entire bodies of software like dinosaurs and much code will

disappear, rarely with major impact. Some will remain with little change and some will change so completely its roots are hard to recognize. In every case, engineers will gauge the benefits and risks of putting a bypass or patch on a hotspot vs. a wider or complete refactoring, with the decision and results depending on the context and the ecosystem around it.

Linux started as a Unix clone, but the pressure on its code quality is so high, it is seriously considering Rust code in critical device drivers when C and Unix were considered symbiotic for decades. And while reimplementing of a full OS like the Linux kernel in formally verified SPARK for airplane or automotive use seems beyond imagination, a refactoring of tiny hypervisors like OKL4 [20]/Sel4 [21], which is already formally verified if in C, is much more likely and could coexist with e.g. a Linux system inside security enclaves (it is used on iPhones), as management engines or run it as guests.

There is no stopping software until it dies or kills

The giggling smart pet we give to our children, the smart baby monitor or light bulb, the last fridge, coffee or washing machines we bought were sold as an improvement over their predecessors, which still used embedded controllers, discrete electronics or even mechanical cores to achieve their function. Their internet connectivity and augmented services were advertised as extra value while in fact all cleverness lies in the employment of a full functional equivalent of Unix mainframe at their core as a cost cutting measure.

That mainframe has shrunk from a full room to less than a fingernail, yet may run much faster with a single battery for life and sell for pennies rather than millions, but by the million as a result. The extremely rich functional base of a full open source Linux software stack allows the vendor to implement the entire functional logic of all these devices in perhaps a couple dozen lines of PHP code by a college student as class assignment. Previously a qualified specialist might have been required and had to use a commercial development

environment for a proprietary embedded OS; similarly, an electrical engineer and various prototype iterations for the discrete electronics or a complete separate assembly line for the mechanical solution might have been needed.

But that mainframe and its software were designed to run accounting and even a moon mission. It was written to correctly process all permutations of well-defined inputs which paid for the expensive mainframe. It wasn't designed to withstand the near infinite cross product of the complementary inputs, almost guaranteed to break it in a manner that can be observed on a digital clone and thus turned into an exploit. It wasn't written to survive immediate attacks from the industrialized cyber-armies, which will convert everything with a known vulnerability into another botnet member. It could still be safe, if it ran well maintained in a secured data centre, behind protective layers of firewalls and intrusion detection systems, instead of your home WiFi. To the MIRAI botnet [20] and for most ransomware trojans these micro mainframes are fully functional giants and offer the additional advantage of well documented vulnerabilities easy to exploit and never closed for lack of an update channel. The potential physical and financial damage from legacy code running on shiny new gadgets vastly outstrips any potential benefit, yet the relentless push for cost reduction and novelty will drive code into your pacemaker, your car, your home, in short everywhere it was never intended to be by those who wrote the vast majority of it, which just got carelessly copied by someone not interested in the implication.

The efforts to contain that risk can't really be bigger than the value gained by expanding the reach of IoT. It is for this

reason that finding cheap replicable countermeasures is one of the highest priorities for any vendor or government trying to create value from information technology today. We highlight some technologies in "Reversing John von Neumann and Steve Jobs, but not software".

References

- [1] Robert H. Dennard, Fritz H. Ghaensslen, Hwa-Nien Yu, V. Leo Rideout, Ernest Bassous, Andre R. Leblanc, "Design of Ion-Implanted MOSFET's with Very Small Physical Dimensions", https://www.ece.ucsb.edu/courses/ECE225/225_W07Banerjee/reference/Dennard.pdf
- [2] Richard W. Hamming, Adward A. Feigenbaum, "Computer Structures: Readings and Examples", Illiac IV, <http://gordonbell.azurewebsites.net/cgb%20files/computer%20structures%20readings%20and%20examples%201971.pdf>
- [3] Galapagos Conservation Trust, "Darwin's Finches", <https://galapagosconservation.org.uk/wildlife/darwins-finches/>
- [4] "Why teach Kotlin", <https://kotlinlang.org/education/why-teach-kotlin.html>
- [5] John Timmer, "A fast look at Swift, Apple's new programming language", <https://arstechnica.com/gadgets/2014/06/a-fast-look-at-swift-apples-new-programming-language/>
- [6] Russ Cox, "Eleven Years of Go", <https://blog.golang.org/11years>
- [7] "Rust, A language empowering everyone to build reliable and efficient software", <https://www.rust-lang.org/>
- [8] SPARK Ada, <https://www.adaic.org/advantages/spark-ada/>
- [9] Jason Fitzpatrick, "If You're Not Paying for It, You're the Product", <https://lifehacker.com/5697167/if-youre-not-paying-for-it-youre-the-product>
- [10] R.W. Bemer, "A View of the History of COBOL", http://archive.computerhistory.org/resources/text/Knuth_Don_X4100/PDF_index/k-8-pdf/k-8-u2776-Honeywell-mag-History-Cobol.pdf
- [11] Rajat Acharya, Nitin F. Pereira, "APL Programming Language", <http://courses.cs.vt.edu/~cs5314/Lang-Paper-Presentation/Papers/HoldPapers/APL.pdf>
- [12] Martin Worthington, "Ancient language of Babylonia is brought back to life", <https://www.alumni.cam.ac.uk/news/ancient-language-of-babylonia-is-brought-back-to-life>
- [13] John Backus, "The History of Fortran I, II and III", <http://www.softwarepreservation.org/projects/FORTRAN/paper/p25-backus.pdf>
- [14] Brian W. Kernighan, Dennis M. Ritchie, "The C Programming Language First Edition", <https://archive.org/details/TheCProgrammingLanguageFirstEdition/page/n7/mode/2up>
- [15] "The Algol Programming Language", <https://web.archive.org/web/20161006113915/http://groups.engin.umd.umich.edu/CIS/course.des/cis400/algol/algol.html>
- [16] Lawrence G. Roberts, "The evolution of Packet Switching", https://web.archive.org/web/20181231092936/http://www.ismlab.usf.edu/dcom/Ch10_Roberts_EvolutionPacketSwitching_IEEE_1978.pdf
- [17] Arjun Singh, Joon Ong, Amit Agarwal, Glen Anderson, Ashby Armistead, Roy Bannon, Seb Boving, Gaurav Desai, Bob Felderman, Paulie Germano, Anand Kanagala, Jeff Provost, Jason Simmons, Eiichi Tanda, Jim Wanderer, Urs Hölzle, Stephen Stuart, and Amin Vahdat, "Jupiter Rising: A Decade of Clos Topologies and Centralized Control in Google's Datacenter Network", <https://dl.acm.org/doi/pdf/10.1145/2829988.2787508>
- [18] H.K. Jerry Chu, Yuna Liu, "Use Space TCP – Getting LKL Read for the Prime Time", <https://storage.googleapis.com/pub-tools-public-publication-data/pdf/6ece8c450ee375eb31b2795a2a227a5d8c3598b7.pdf>
- [19] Alessandro Ghedini, "Make SSL boring again", <https://blog.cloudflare.com/make-ssl-boring-again>
- [20] General Dynamics, "Hypervisor", <https://gdmissionsystems.com/products/cross-domain-solutions/hypervisor>
- [21] "The seL4* Microkernel", <https://sel4.systems/>
- [22] Paras Jha, "Who is Anna-Senpai, the Mirai Worm Author?", <https://krebsonsecurity.com/2017/01/who-is-anna-senpai-the-mirai-worm-author/>

Thomas Hoberg is Technical Director R&D at Worldline, Germany.

This document is part of the HiPEAC Vision available at hipeac.net/vision.

This is release v.1, January 2021.

Cite as: T. Hoberg. Extreme reuse: the only future any code can afford. In M. Duranton et al., editors, HiPEAC Vision 2021, pages 176-183, Jan 2021.

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.4719690

The HiPEAC project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement number 871174.

© HiPEAC 2021